

Editorial

Artificial intelligence in higher education: Teaching and learning in an AI-powered world

Ioanna Anninou^{1*}, Georgia Stavraki², Jashim Khan³

¹Surrey Business School, University of Surrey, United Kingdom

²International Hellenic University, Greece

³Yoobee College of Creative Innovation, New Zealand.

*Correspondence: E-mail: i.anninou@surrey.ac.uk

Abstract

The aim of this introduction and special issue is to explore Artificial Intelligence (hereinafter AI) in higher education and examine its implications for teaching and learning in an AI-powered world. This special issue contains five articles that discuss themes such as the opportunities and challenges, biases and divides, and teachers' perceptions of AI: their hopes, concerns, and ethics. The issue concludes with a forward-looking 'metacognitive creative destruction' theme recognizing how teaching and learning evolves in an AI-powered world. Through this special issue we attempt to further enrich current research on AI in higher education by balancing its transformative potential with a consideration of its ethical, reflective, and pedagogical challenges.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence; Higher Education; Teaching and Learning; AI Ethics; Teacher Perceptions; Metacognition; Educational Innovation.*

1. Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (hereinafter AI) is a computational machine learning system that performs tasks requiring human intelligence, such as understanding language, recognising patterns, and making decisions (see Herman & Puntoni, 2024; Huang & Rust, 2021). In this light, AI involves processes such as "learning, adaptation, synthesis, and self-correction" through the analysis and use of data (Singh & Hiran, 2022, p. 136). AI is transforming most realms of human activity such as tourism, healthcare, and retailing to name a few (e.g. Dwivedi et al., 2024; Kim & Park, 2025; Noble & Mende, 2023). It also has a profound effect on teaching and learning in higher education (Barros et al., 2023), especially through Generative AI (hereinafter GenAI) applications. Indeed, technology, no matter some barriers it might pose (e.g., digital divide, Fisk et al., 2023), it has played a focal point in education by enabling the distribution of knowledge.

In this special issue, we present a collection of articles that enrich current understanding of AI-powered higher education from the perspectives of both educators and students. AI in education has not only attracted attention but has also generated both opportunities and challenges; learners benefit from access to personalised information, and educators realise the benefits of using AI for administrative tasks, while also expressing concerns about copyright, information literacy, and misinformation (e.g. Liu et al., 2025; Urban et al., 2025). Acknowledging that the impact of AI on higher education is multidimensional, for the purposes of the current special issue, we group this impact into the following categories: administration, instruction, teaching and learning experience, assessment, and integrity.

Specifically, the use of AI in administrative tasks in higher education includes streamlining processes such as attendance, grading, and providing student feedback (Er et al., 2024). AI enabled platforms such as Moodle, Blackboard, and Microsoft's Power BI support educators to track routine tasks and generate metrics, including contact hours,

student enrollment, academic progression, graduation data, satisfaction surveys, and performance gaps (Bohlens, 2026). These routine-based activities can facilitate a smoother execution of institution-wide duties. For instance, by automating routine tasks, AI allows educators to focus on instructional content, by achieving time efficiencies and improving instructional effectiveness and output (see Topali et al., 2025).

Moreover, instructors utilise AI tools to improve the quality of instructional content (Warren et al., 2026), ranging from devising assessment strategies, creating new content, improving the delivery options, and at the same time balancing the workload to support learners' knowledge absorption. AI also provides opportunities for educators to employ AI in personal tutoring. As such, some tutoring tasks are fully or partly administered using AI, while educators focus on developing strategies empowering, in this manner, students to achieve their learning goals (Hu et al., 2024). Indeed, an AI-enabled tutor not only offers flexible learning options but also allows learners to take control of their learning activities (Yang, 2026). This is because an AI-powered learner-centric approach enables students to achieve their learning goals. The learning goals are achieved when the appropriate processes (e.g., setting appropriate goals or checking AI material accuracy) are activated to deepen interactions with AI tools (ibid).

Such use of AI in learning is also favored by parents for routine tasks (e.g., arithmetic tasks) and can be valuable for creating optimal learning experiences based on content customisation (Shao et al., 2025). This applies to both web-based education, which is undergoing transformational shifts, and to learners' growing preference for AI-based tutors in such environments (Maphalala et al., 2025). The AI-enabled, web-based online education and 24/7 tutoring options exemplify positive AI-facilitated learning by engaging students when they are mentally prepared and can engage with the learning content (Latif et al., 2026; Wang et al., 2026). Examples of AI-based personal tutoring systems take a pedagogical approach and aim to support learners in understanding, retaining, and applying knowledge. As such, tutoring systems, by considering students' needs, cocreate learning with them.

At the other end, main concerns raised relate to assessments including academic integrity and the potential promotion of dishonesty when GenAI is used to replace critical thinking and writing skills, alongside the uncertainty created by AI detection software. All of these are recognised on a case-by-case basis in higher education, depending on the context of learning goals (Corbin et al., 2025; Hurley et al., 2026). At the same time, wider concerns about AI's potential negative impact on learning are widely discussed (Essien et al., 2024; Fan et al., 2025). However, the promising potential of AI use could override these risks, such as employing AI to predict which students are at risk of failing and offer intervention (Hu et al., 2024). When the students' overall wellbeing is considered and care is given when designing such support systems, previously disadvantaged and vulnerable students, such as those living in poverty or from minority groups, can gain from such AI intervention (Prinsloo et al., 2024).

To this end, the studies hosted in this special issue discuss interactions occurring between AI technologies—focusing mainly on GenAI—and higher education, centering on their effects on stakeholders such as students, educators, institutions, and businesses. This special issue features both conceptual and empirical analyses of learning and pedagogical practices and their interrelationships, striving to deliver meaningful, ethical, and engaging interactions. Before presenting the papers hosted in this issue, we draw upon the discourses these papers generate and discuss the implications of AI in higher education.

2. AI and higher education

The Digital Education Council (2024) survey of 3,839 responses from 16 countries reveals that 86% of university students use AI tools to assist with their studies, with 24% using them daily. Participants revealed they use AI for information search, grammar, condensing and summarising information. While AI has the potential to improve quality and customisation, recent studies (e.g., Saeger et al., 2024; Stoyanova & Angelova, 2024) argue that AI can improve the quality of written communication, but at the same time AI carries the potential to incite plagiarism, reduce accuracy, compromise

privacy, and lead to the loss of skills (Ivanov, 2023). As AI continues to evolve, educators face both the opportunities and challenges of addressing AI's impact on teaching methods, content creation, assessment, and personalisation (Richter et al., 2024).

2.1 Opportunities and challenges of AI in higher education

Doğan *et al.*, (2025) and Eltharif and Abdalla (2025) caution that the balance between AI possibilities and associated risks requires a full assessment before issuing a remark to users in higher education. The promise of AI in higher education stems from its power to automate mundane and administrative tasks (Khairullah *et al.*, 2025), to allow for personalised and gamified learning that stimulate engagement and involvement (Kohnke & Moorhouse, 2025; Shao *et al.*, 2025), and to boost accessibility for students with disabilities (Omiegbe, 2024; Owoseni *et al.*, 2024).

AI-intensified transformation of administrative tasks, such as admissions, attendance, timetabling, faculty management, grievance or financial aid handling, and accreditation documentation, can have positive effects to higher education. The use of AI in administrative tasks reduces bottlenecks, unlocks innovation, and increases student satisfaction (Khairullah *et al.*, 2025) by improving operational and other efficiencies (e.g., learning and accessibility to education). The use of AI in higher education accommodates students with learning disabilities and language barriers (Owoseni *et al.*, 2024) as it allows for real-time feedback that improves student engagement and success.

The other side is negative, pointing to the adverse consequences of AI in higher education. The risk of AI in education mainly concerns the issue of academic integrity and what we know of academic cheating (Ivanov, 2023), incorrect information (Ivanov & Soliman, 2023), and biased algorithms (Arora *et al.*, 2023). One major concern is data colonialism (Ahmed, 2026) which treats personal information as a resource for profit and control, with some studies aiming to understand how global AI governance is locally imagined and legitimised (Chung, 2026, p. 909). Couldry and Meijas (2019) compare data colonialism to the exploitation associated with historical colonisation, showing how data from people's lives is extracted and used. Thus, one threat derives from the use of students' data in profit-making ventures of the AI organisations. Scholars (Ahmed, 2026; Cruz-Jesus *et al.* 2016) also caution that concentration of digital knowledge production, data collection and surveillance in developed countries (Zembylas, 2024) is likely to set apart the distinction between those countries that have infrastructure to support AI and those that do not, causing digital divide and inequality in AI-supported higher education. The digital divide between countries threatens fair education. Thus, employing AI in education deepens social inequalities and divides the less wealthy communities (Arora *et al.*, 2023).

In the negative outlook of AI, AI represents a 'techno-deterministic perspective', that is, AI is perceived as the primary, autonomous driver of social and cultural change, influencing life rather than being determined by it. However, Chatzichristofis (2026) recognizes that humans shape how AI is used, rather than the other way around. This raises questions into the notion of human agency and authority. Marketisation has already taken place in higher education. The shift from educator-learner relations towards a supplier-consumer model (Molesworth *et al.*, 2009) goes further when AI creates a middleman-consumer model. The educator likely becomes a curator rather than a knowledge producer.

2.2 Artificial intelligence in education: Pedagogy before technology

Current discourses regarding the prevalence of AI technology in education focus on what technology can do rather than what it should do to enable meaningful learning, thus raising the question of whether pedagogy dictates technology or vice versa. Pachler et al. (2025) critically examine techno-solutionism, namely a view explaining that technological tools alone can meet complex educational challenges. Fletcher (2025) challenges such an approach and argues that a range of factors, including commercial, social, technological, and pedagogical factors, converge to produce artificial pedagogies,

which are still in their early stages (Pachler et al., 2025). For example, within the higher education context, the role of AI in educators' decisions about student outcomes remains debated (Al-Mamary et al., 2025). If an educator does not understand why AI suggested a particular learning pathway or graded an essay in a certain way, they cannot properly guide the student, diagnose misconceptions, and develop skills central to meaningful learning. This would pose a question: Which came first, pedagogy or technology?

Pedagogical beliefs also influence an educator's interpretations of AI in higher education (Wang et al., 2026). Educators evaluate whether AI use aligns with their pedagogical values but also their ability to utilize it, thereby, pedagogical values and ability determine acceptance or rejection of AI in their teaching practice (Choi et al., 2023). Beyond simply accepting, a relationship of *symbiosis* between educators and AI has been suggested, representing an intentional, conscious and mindful process of AI adoption (Fukami et al., 2025, p. 3). Both acceptance and symbiosis, are based on AI's responsible use (Fukami et al., 2025) but also require upskilling and instructor training programs before the application of AI in higher education institutions is implemented (Choi et al., 2023; Fukami et al., 2025; Garzón et al., 2025). Ultimately, while AI can be a powerful instrument in education, it should not be treated as a techno-solutionist remedy for education challenges. Its assimilation must be guided by ongoing critical reflection on its social, economic, and ethical impacts (Thibaud, 2025).

2.3 Ethical concerns of artificial intelligence in education

A stream of research focuses on ethical concerns that have always been central to educational practice (Ajani et al., 2024; Chelghoum & Chelghoum, 2025; Darwin et al., 2024). These concerns are data privacy, lack of human involvement, the possibility of plagiarism, and data security. At a macro level, Ajani et al. (2024) caution that the digital divide is a major challenge of AI in higher education. The concern is that the inclusion of AI in higher education will cause the exclusion of learners on the global stage and create disparities in access to AI between advanced and non-advanced economies. Apart from the digital divide, Darwin et al. (2024) thought AI might aid students in learning instructional content but hinder or undermine the development of critical thinking and writing skills. Similarly, students who may not have access to AI tools globally may feel marginalised (Sato et al., 2024). The ethics of AI in higher education institutions include the rights to authorship, copyright, and data ownership, as well as considerations on who oversees the inputs and outputs of GenAI tools (Chelghoum & Chelghoum, 2025). Such ethical concerns are raised in this special issue.

2.4 Looking ahead: Human thinking in the age of artificial intelligence

As AI takes over tasks requiring human intelligence, questions arise about which cognitive abilities remain unique to humans. The concept of creative metacognition, refined in the context of AI as 'Metacognitive Creative Destruction', provides a new theoretical framework for understanding how educational innovation develops through cognitive transformation in AI-enhanced environments. AI tools are performing tasks that generally require intelligence, such as retrieving information, generating information from memory, processing information, and dealing with ambiguity in decision-making. A question arises as to which cognitive capacities are unique to humans, and which are performed by AI (Yan et al., 2024). As such, with the advent of AI, this relates to understanding creative metacognition (von Thienen et al., 2023). In this light, a novel theoretical framework is articulated in this issue: Metacognitive Creative Destruction, which suggests that individuals discard outdated knowledge and pursue learning as a continuous spiral. This demands learners to reflect on their cognitive processes, question existing knowledge and challenge outdated knowledge. This fosters the reconstruction of new knowledge through a recursive and iterative process involving reflection, questioning, unlearning, and growth. While AI enhances metacognitive capacity and creative reconstruction, it cannot replace the uniquely human ability for reflective judgment and intentional unlearning.

3. Articles featured in this special issue

Our call for papers attracted submissions from diverse geographic regions and institutional backgrounds, resulting in global coverage of AI in higher education. The five accepted papers address key debates outlined in this introduction.

Paper 1: Artificial intelligence in contemporary higher education: Opportunities and challenges

This commentary articulates the opportunities and challenges of AI in higher education. The authors highlight algorithmic bias, data colonialism, the digital divide and inequalities, and a lack of human agency and authority in decision-making as challenges. The paper argues that hyper-personalisation risks turning educators into content curators and feedback is likely to be complemented by AI tutors. AI has the potential to automate tasks, personalise learning, improve accessibility (e.g., for students with disabilities and language barriers), enhance student engagement through AI-powered tutoring and virtual labs, and reduce administrative burdens. The paper concludes that the future of AI depends on ethical choices and mirrors societal values.

Paper 2: Artificial intelligence in language education: Teachers' fears, hopes and solutions

This paper is a commentary of the findings of a comparative multi-country study of 636 language teachers from Brazil, Finland, Hong Kong, and South Korea, examining their perceptions and experiences of AI in higher education. Overall, responses reflect positive attitudes towards AI, with slight regional variation. South Korean teachers show high confidence but moderate trust in pedagogical application. Hong Kong teachers displayed high expectations with lower confidence, influenced by policy. Finnish teachers were reflective and ethically aware but had low self-efficacy. Brazilian teachers expressed enthusiasm but faced challenges due to uneven access. Three key themes emerged in this study: self-efficacy, pedagogical orientation and policy. The paper concludes that successful AI application in higher education requires educator training, inclusivity, ethical design tools and teacher advocacy.

Paper 3: Generative artificial intelligence and ethics: University faculty, staff, and students' views

The study, "Generative AI and Ethics", is an exploratory study at a mid-Atlantic University that captures perceptions of AI prior to the launch of GenAI to the general public in 2023. 256 faculty, staff and students participated in this study. The study finds that accessibility, efficiency, academic integrity, plagiarism, algorithmic bias, critical thinking, and data privacy are key factors influencing AI in higher education settings. The study highlights a need for policies on what constitutes plagiarism, equity-focused implementation, and faculty training. It concludes by recommending a University Generative AI Ethics Checklist.

Paper 4: Artificial intelligence and teaching practice: Pre-service teachers' perceptions in Greece

This study examines pre-service primary school teachers in Greece to understand their familiarity with AI, their attitudes toward its use in education, and how they apply it in their teaching practice, using a questionnaire based on the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge) model. Participants are familiar with AI and have used AI applications (mainly ChatGPT and similar tools), primarily for lesson planning and content preparation. Participants in this study report that their use of AI during teaching practice is limited; they recognise the benefits in terms of time saved on administrative tasks, but express caution about a lack of trust in AI and its reliability. In this study, three themes emerge: pragmatic acceptance of AI, cautious and selective use, and practical barriers. The paper concludes that while pre-service teachers recognise the potential of AI, their lack of pedagogical understanding of its uses understates it.

Paper 5: Disruptive learning in the artificial intelligence era: A metacognitive creative destruction model for educational innovation

The aim of this paper is to validate the Metacognitive Creative Destruction (MCD) model. The model explains how disruptive innovations such as AI originate from cognitive destruction and reconstruct new learning and knowledge. The theoretical framework for this model is drawn from Schumpeter's theory of creative destruction. A survey of 1,498 participants in Greece revealed that adaptive capacities, contextual factors, and learning outcomes confirm the explanatory power of the MCD model, indicating that metacognitive flexibility and creative reconstruction improve innovation and adaptability. AI aids metacognition but does not directly influence unlearning.

4. Conclusions and Future Directions

This special issue brings together a series of multifaceted papers and examines the impact of AI on higher education, unravelling a central tension: AI offers opportunities – automating administrative tasks, enabling personalised learning, improving accessibility, and fostering learner engagement through AI tutoring – yet simultaneously raises ethical, pedagogical, and social challenges. The concerns raised in this issue regarding AI in higher education are data privacy, lack of human involvement, academic integrity, algorithmic bias, digital divides, and erosion of decision-making autonomy.

A common theme in the papers is the critique of techno-solutionism, i.e., the belief that technology alone can solve educational challenges. Contributors argue that effective AI integration requires a focus on pedagogical values, teacher training, and critical reflection. The Metacognitive Creative Destruction (MCD) model highlights that while AI can enhance metacognitive skills and creativity, it cannot replace essential human abilities like reflective judgment, epistemic humility, and intentional unlearning.

References

- Ahmed, S.A., (2026). Algorithmic dependence and digital colonialism: a conceptual framework for artificial intelligence in education and knowledge systems of the Global South. *Frontiers in Education*, 11, pp. 1720563.
- Ajani, O. A., Akintolu, M. and Afolabi, S. O. (2024). The emergence of artificial intelligence in higher education: Prospects and challenges of AI. *International Journal of Research in Business & Social Science*, 13(8), pp. 157-165.
- Al-Mamary, Y. H., Alfalah, A. A., Shamsuddin, A. and Abubakar, A. A. (2025). Artificial intelligence powering education: ChatGPT's impact on students' academic performance through the lens of technology-to-performance chain theory. *Journal of Applied Research in Higher Education*, 17(5), pp. 1661-1679.
- Arora, A., Barrett, M., Lee, E., Oborn, E. and Prince, K. (2023). Risk and the future of AI: Algorithmic bias, data colonialism, and marginalisation. *Information and Organisation*, 33(3), pp. 100478.
- Barros, A., Prasad, A. and Śliwa, M. (2023). Generative artificial intelligence and academia: Implication for research, teaching and service. *Management Learning*, 54(5), pp. 597-604.
- Bohlens, C. (2026). Predictive analytics in student performance and retention strategies: AI predicts risk, guides support, and boosts students (pp. 57-86). In R. M. Abdelaal S., & M. Kayyali (Ed.) *AI-Powered Pedagogy, Academic Transformation, and Faculty Empowerment*. IGI Global Scientific Publishing.
- Chatzichristofis, S. A. (2026). Reframing AI in education: A pedagogical opportunity, not a technocratic threat. *Journal of Research in Science Teaching*, 63(1), pp. 97-103.
- Chelghoum, H. and Chelghoum, A. (2025). Artificial intelligence in education: Opportunities, challenges, and ethical concerns. *Journal of Studies in Language, Culture and Society (JSLCS)*, 8(1), pp. 1-14.
- Choi, S., Jang, Y. and Kim, H. (2023). Influence of pedagogical beliefs and perceived trust on teachers' acceptance of educational artificial intelligence tools. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 39(4), pp. 910-922.

- Chung, H. F. (2026). Betting on (un) certain futures: Sociotechnical imaginaries of AI and varieties of techno-developmentalism in Asia. *Information, Communication & Society*, 29(3), pp. 909-926.
- Corbin, T., Bearman, M., Boud, D. and Dawson, P. (2025). The wicked problem of AI and assessment. *Assessment & evaluation in higher education*, pp. 1-17.
- Couldry, N., and Mejias, U. A. (2019). *The costs of connection: How data is colonising human life and appropriating it for capitalism* (4th ed.). Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Cruz-Jesus, F., Vicente, M. R., Bacao, F. and Oliveira, T. (2016). The education-related digital divide: An analysis for the EU-28. *Computers in Human Behaviour*, 56, pp. 72-82.
- Darwin, Rusdin, D., Mukminatien, N., Suryati, N., Laksmi, E. D. and Marzuki. (2024). Critical thinking in the AI era: An exploration of EFL students' perceptions, benefits, and limitations. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), pp. 2290342.
- Digital Education Council. (2024). *Global AI student survey 2024: AI or not AI—What students want*. [What Students Want: Key Results from DEC Global AI Student Survey 2024](#). Accessed the 10th of May 2026, at 18.08.
- Doğan, M., Celik, A. and Arslan, H. (2025). AI in higher education: Risks and opportunities from the academician perspective. *European Journal of Education*, 60(1), pp. e12863.
- Dwivedi, Y. K., Pandey, N., Currie, W. and Micu, A. (2024). Leveraging ChatGPT and other generative artificial intelligence (AI)-based applications in the hospitality and tourism industry: practices, challenges and research agenda. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 36(1), pp. 1-12.
- Eltharif, A. A. M. and Abdalla, R. A. S. A. (2025). Conceptual framework for identifying risks of AI integration in higher education. *International Journal of Computer Applications*, 975, pp. 8887.
- Er, E., Akçapınar, G., Bayazıt, A., Noroozi, O. and Banihashem, S. K. (2025). Assessing student perceptions and use of instructor versus AI-generated feedback. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 56(3), pp. 1074-1091.
- Essien, A., Bukoye, O. T., O'Dea, X. and Kremantzis, M. (2024). The influence of AI text generators on critical thinking skills in UK business schools. *Studies in Higher Education*, 49(5), pp. 865-882.
- Fan, Y., Tang, L., Le, H., Shen, K., Tan, S., Zhao, Y., Shen, Y., Li, X. and Gašević, D. (2025). Beware of metacognitive laziness: Effects of generative artificial intelligence on learning motivation, processes, and performance. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 56(2), pp. 489-530.
- Fisk, R. P., Gallan, A. S., Joubert, A. M., Beekhuyzen, J., Cheung, L. and Russell-Bennett, R. (2023). Healing the digital divide with digital inclusion: enabling human capabilities. *Journal of Service Research*, 26(4), pp. 542-559.
- Fletcher, R. (2025). Technological solutionism: Disability, higher education and generative artificial intelligence. *Disability & Society*, 1-6.
- Fukami, C. V., Hamilton, A. L., Rivers, C., Holland, A., Brady, M., Fellenz, M., ... and Leben, D. (2025). Human-centered business education in an artificial intelligence-driven world. *Journal of Management Inquiry*, pp. 10564926251364213.
- Garzón, J., Patiño, E. and Marulanda, C. (2025). Systematic review of artificial intelligence in education: Trends, benefits, and challenges. *Multimodal Technologies and Interaction*, 9(8), pp. 84.
- Hermann, E. and Puntoni, S. (2024). Artificial intelligence and consumer behavior: From predictive to generative AI. *Journal of Business Research*, 180, 114720.
- Hu, Y. H., Fu, J. S. and Yeh, H. C. (2024). Developing an early-warning system through robotic process automation: Are intelligent tutoring robots as effective as human teachers?. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 32(6), pp. 2803-2816.
- Huang, M.-H., and Rust, R. T. (2021b). A strategic framework for artificial intelligence in marketing. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 49(1), 30-50.
- Hurley, M., Casey, D., Morari, V. and Grimes, D. (2026). Where to from here? On the borders of academic integrity, academic misconduct, and assessment security after GenAI. *Studies in Higher Education*, pp. 1-14.

- Ivanov, S. (2023). The dark side of artificial intelligence in higher education. *The Service Industries Journal*, 43(15–16), pp.1055-1082.
- Ivanov, S. and Soliman, M. (2023). Game of algorithms: ChatGPT implications for the future of tourism education and research. *Journal of Tourism Futures*, 9(2), pp. 214-221.
- Khairullah, S. A., Harris, S., Hadi, H. J., Sandhu, R. A., Ahmad, N. and Alshara, M. A. (2025). Implementing artificial intelligence in academic and administrative processes through responsible strategic leadership in the higher education institutions. *Frontiers in Education*, 10, pp. 1548104.
- Kim, H. and Park, J. (2025). Artificial intelligence applications in digital healthcare marketing: A systematic assessment. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 198, pp. 122456.
- Kohnke, L. and Moorhouse, B. L. (2025). Enhancing the emotional aspects of language education through generative artificial intelligence (GenAI): A qualitative investigation. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 167, pp. 108600.
- Latif, E., Liu, V. and Zhai, X. (2026). A systematic review of intelligent and robot tutoring systems: Evolution, pedagogical design, and AI-driven classification. *Smart Learning Environments*, 13(1), pp. 1.
- Liu, M., Zhang, L. J. and Zhang, D. (2025). Enhancing student GAI literacy in digital multimodal composing through development and validation of a scale. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 166, pp. 108569.
- Maphalala, M. C., Mkhasibe, R. G. and Mncube, D. W. (2025). Exploring the roles of AI-powered e-tutors in enhancing self-directed learning in open distance e-learning courses. *Interdisciplinary Journal of Education Research*, 7(1), pp. a12-a12.
- Molesworth, M., Nixon, E. and Scullion, R. (2009). Having, being and higher education: The marketisation of the university and the transformation of the student into consumer. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 14(3), pp. 277-287.
- Noble, S. M. and Mende, M. (2023). The future of artificial intelligence and robotics in the retail and service sector: Sketching the field of consumer-robot-experiences. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 51(4), pp. 747-756.
- Omiegbe, O. (2024). Artificial intelligence in higher education: Bridging the gap for students with disabilities. *British Journal of Education*, 12(12), pp. 38-50.
- Owoseni, A., Kolade, O. and Egbetokun, A. (2024). Enhancing personalised learning and student engagement using generative AI (pp. 123-150). In A. Owoseni, O. Kolade, & A. Egbetokun (Ed.) *Generative AI in Higher Education*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Pachler, N., Turvey, K. and Abaci, S. (2025). AI solutionism and the techno/human-centric remediation of agency in higher education (pp. 91-114). In M. A. Peters, O. Kamenarac, B. J. Green, P. Jandrić, & T. Besley (Ed.) *Postdigital Education for Development*. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Prinsloo, P., Khalil, M. and Slade, S. (2024). Vulnerable student digital well-being in AI-powered educational decision support systems (AI-EDSS) in higher education. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 55(5), pp. 2075-2092.
- Richter, S., Giroux, M., Piven, I., Sima, H. and Dodd, P. (2024). A constructivist approach to integrating AI in marketing education: Bridging theory and practice. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 47(2), pp. 94-111.
- Saeger, K. J., Finley, L. R. and Wickam, M. J. (2024). The AI revolution: Awareness of and readiness for AI-based digital tools and technologies in business education. *Journal of Research in Business Education*, 64(1), pp. 1-25.
- Shao, A., Lu, Z., Zhong, B., Liu, S. Q. and Lu, W. (2025). Human touch vs. AI tech: Understanding user preferences in the future of education. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 164, pp. 108492.
- Singh, S. V. and Hiran, K. K. (2022). The impact of AI on teaching and learning in higher education technology. *Journal of Higher Education Theory and Practice*, 22(13), pp. 135-148.
- Stoyanova, T. and Angelova, M. (2024). Good practices in the use of artificial intelligence for the digitalisation of higher education. *Journal of Entrepreneurship & Sustainability Issues*, 11(4), pp. 44-62.

- Thibaud, E. (2025). Reflections on techno-solutionism in education: Manifestations and causes. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, pp. 1-12.
- Topali, P., Haelermans, C., Molenaar, I. and Segers, E. (2025). Pedagogical considerations in the automation era: A systematic literature review of AIED in K-12 authentic settings. *British Educational Research Journal*, 51(6), pp. 2777-2809.
- Urban, M., Brom, C., Lukavský, J., Děchtěrenko, F., Hein, V., Svacha, F., ... and Urban, K. (2025). "ChatGPT can make mistakes. Check important info." Epistemic beliefs and metacognitive accuracy in students' integration of ChatGPT content into academic writing. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 56(5), pp. 1897-1918.
- von Thienen, J. P., Weinstein, T. J. and Meinel, C. (2023). Creative metacognition in design thinking: Exploring theories, educational practices, and their implications for measurement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, pp. 1157001.
- Wang, W., Wang, Y., Chen, J., Wang, X., Zhang, H., Guo, C. and Peng, Y. (2026). The effectiveness of AI-supported personalized feedback on students' learning outcomes and motivation: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 64(3), pp. 724-755.
- Warren, S. J., Boston Vogt, E., Tincher, B. and Yang, J. (2026). Enhancing quality assurance through strategic artificial intelligence integration: A framework for higher education digital transformation. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 34(2), pp. 205-222.
- Yan, L., Greiff, S., Teuber, Z. and Gašević, D. (2024). Promises and challenges of generative artificial intelligence for human learning. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 8(10), pp. 1839-1850.
- Yang, S. C. (2026). Integrating technology acceptance, self-determination, and self-regulation: A structural model of generative AI-supported learning and competence. *Computers in Human Behavior*, pp. 108933.
- Zembylas, M. (2024). Decolonising data in higher education: Critical issues and future directions. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 0(0), pp. 1-12.

Biographical Notes: Ioanna Anninou is Associate Professor of Marketing at Surrey Business School, University of Surrey. Her research interests focus on customer experience, consumer emotions and the use of innovative assessments in higher education. Ioanna is a Senior Fellow of the Higher Education Academy (SFHE), and in her teaching practice she explores different approaches to enhancing student engagement and soft skills such as creativity, problem-solving, and critical thinking. She has published in journals like *European Journal of Marketing*, *Management Learning* and the *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. Her research has been presented at international conferences. Georgia Stavragi is Assistant Professor of Marketing at the International Hellenic University, Greece. Her research interests lie in the areas of experiential consumption, arts marketing, visual research methods in consumer behaviour and consumers' identity projects. She has published in academic outlets including *Management Learning*, *European Journal of Marketing*, and *Qualitative Market Research*, among others. Her work has also appeared in books and international conferences. Jashim Khan is Associate Professor of Marketing and currently Programme Lead - Design Faculty at Yoobee College of Creative Innovation, New Zealand. He has previously held positions at the University of Surrey, UK, and Dongbei University of Finance and Economics, China. He earned a Doctorate in Business Marketing from Auckland University of Technology and a Master of Management (with distinction) from Massey University, New Zealand. His research focuses on understanding the influence of emerging technologies on human behaviour. His work has appeared in various international journals, including the *Journal of Business Research*, *Journal of Economic Psychology*, *Association for Consumer Research*, *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, *International Journal of Non-profit and Voluntary Sector Marketing*, *Journal of Wine Research*, *International Journal of Wine Business Research*, *International Journal of Online Marketing*, *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, *Journal of Marketing for Higher Education*, *Qualitative Market Research*, *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*, *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, and the *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*.